

Extraction Chromatography of Indium(III) on Silica Gel impregnated with High Molecular Weight Carboxylic Acid and its Analytical Applications

PARTHA S. MAJUMDAR and UDAY S. RAY*

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan-731 235

Manuscript received 17 September 1990, revised 26 February 1991, accepted 20 March 1991

Indium(III) was separated by extraction chromatography with Versatic 10 as a stationary phase on a column of silica gel from acetic acid and sodium acetate solution (pH 4.5–6.0). The optimum condition for extraction was studied based on the critical study of the relevant factors as effects of pH, flow rate on extraction and elution. Role of stripping agents on the elution was studied. The separation of indium from a number of elements was carried out. Indium(III) was separated from Al^{III} , Ga^{III} , Tl^{III} , Zr^{IV} and trivalent lanthanides which interfere under the recommended extraction condition by exploiting the differences in their stripping behaviour.

ION-exchange procedure for the separation of trivalent metal ions like aluminium, gallium, indium and thallium through the formation of an ionic complexes with chloride and bromide has been reported¹. Trioctyl phosphine oxide (TOPO)² coated on silica gel column has been used for the extractive chromatographic studies of indium(III) from hydrochloric acid. Isoamyl acetate³ has been used for the separation of In^{III} from Al^{III} and Tl^{III} . High molecular weight carboxylic acids (C_{15} – C_{16}) have been widely used for the solvent extraction studies of di-, tri- and tetravalent metal ions from aqueous solution^{4,5}. Based on this fact a new and improved separation procedure has been developed through reversed phase extraction chromatographic technique which can separate milligram amounts of indium(III) from other elements.

Experimental

An Elico LI-120 digital pH meter and chromatographic column (1.5 × 7.5 cm) of borosil glass was used. Versatic 10, a mixture of high molecular weight C_{10} isomeric tertiary monocarboxylic acid, was used as liquid cation exchanger⁶. A stock solution of In^{III} was prepared by dissolving $\text{In}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ (1.73 g) in HNO_3 (10 ml) and diluted to 250 ml with deionised water, and standardised complexometrically with EDTA⁶.

Silica gel (30–120 mesh, BDH) was rendered hydrophobic by exposing it to the vapours of dimethyl dichlorosilane in nitrogen atmosphere⁷, then washed with methanol and dried at 100°. It was impregnated with Versatic 10 diluted in benzene and dried. The excess organic extractant present in the exchanger was washed with 2M HCl. 1 ml of dimethyl dichlorosilane was adequate for 10 g of silica gel, and 1 g of hydrophobic gel was found to

take up about 0.8 ml of Versatic 10. For column operation impregnated silica gel (3 g) was taken with water, each column being used for 40–45 times.

General extraction procedure: An aqueous solution containing In^{III} (2.1 mg) was mixed with acetic acid (10 ml) and sodium acetate buffer solution and its pH was adjusted to 4.5. The solution was passed through silica gel column coated with Versatic 10 at a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹. pH in the column was adjusted to 4.5 before passing the metal ion solution in each operation. Indium(III) was eluted with a variety of mineral acid and salt solutions and its amount in each fraction (10 ml) was determined complexometrically.

Results and Discussion

The extraction behaviour of indium(III) with Versatic 10 was studied at different pH, keeping its concentration constant. The extraction of indium(III) increased with increase in pH and became quantitative at pH 4.5–6.

Eluting agents: Mineral acids were found efficient eluting agents at lower concentrations. Acids like HNO_3 , HCl, H_2SO_4 and salts like NaCl, NaNO_3 were tested as the eluants. The results show that stripping of indium(III) was complete with 0.01M HNO_3 , 0.1M HCl and 0.1M H_2SO_4 . Water, NaCl and NaNO_3 are very poor eluting agent. A 0.1M HNO_3 was used for the elution of indium(III) in most of the cases.

Exchange capacity: The exchange capacity of the exchanger was determined at different temperatures by measuring the number of milligram equivalent of sodium ion which are absorbed by 1 g of the dry exchanger in the hydrogen form. The exchanger (1 g) was equilibrated with NaOH for 5 h at different temperature. The hydrogen ion libera-

ted was determined titrimetrically. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EXCHANGE CAPACITY AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. °C	Amount of exchanger (g)	Vol. of NaCl (ml) 12.5 M	Vol. of NaOH (ml) 0.188 M	Exchange capacity (meq. of H ⁺ /g)
10	1.002 2	20	15	2.52
15	1.004 0	20	15	2.50
20	1.007 8	20	15	2.48
30	1.005 9	20	15	2.47
40	1.001 8	20	15	2.40
50	1.003 8	20	15	2.38

Separation of In^{III} from binary mixtures : Indium(III) was separated from binary mixtures by exploiting the differences in pH for extraction and through stripping behaviour. Metal ions not sorbed on the column were passed through at pH 4.5. Fe^{III}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and U^{VI} do not interfere, whereas Cr^{III}, Al^{III}, Tl^{III}, Ga^{III}, La^{III}, Dy^{III}, Zr^{IV} and Th^{IV} interfere under the extraction condition ; their interferences were removed by using selective eluants. A binary mixture of these metal ions containing indium(III) was passed through the column at pH 4.5 and all the elements were extracted. During the separation of Cr^{III}, Zr^{IV}, Ce^{IV} and Th^{IV} from In^{III} the column was first eluted with 0.01M HNO₃ for the elution of indium, then other elements were eluted with 1M H₂SO₄ (Cr), 4M HNO₃ (Zr), 1M HNO₃ (Ce and Th). In case of mixtures containing Al^{III}, Tl^{III}, La^{III} and Dy^{III} with In^{III}, Al^{III} was eluted with deionised water, La^{III} and Dy^{III} were eluted with 5 × 10⁻⁴ M HNO₃, Tl^{III} was eluted with 2M NaCl and In^{III} was eluted with 0.01M HNO₃. After separation these metal ions were estimated complexometrically.

Separation of In^{III} from multicomponent mixtures : The technique has been applied to separate indium from groups of elements which are co-extracted in Versatic 10 by exploiting the differences in stripping behaviour. Different concentration of mineral acids and salts were used in these separations. Indium was separated from a mixture containing Al^{III}, Tl^{III} and Ga^{III} by passing the mixture through the column at pH 4.5. Al^{III} was first stripped with deionised water, In^{III} with 0.01 M HCl, Ga^{III} with 1M HCl and Tl^{III} with 2M NaCl. A mixture of In^{III}, Al^{III}, Cr^{III} and Zn^{II} was passed through the column at pH 4.5. when all the metals were extracted except Zn^{II}. Al^{III} was stripped with deionised water, In^{III} with 0.01M HNO₃, and Cr^{III} with 1M H₂SO₄. A mixture of In^{III}, U^{VI}, Ce^{IV} and Zr^{IV} was passed through the column at pH 4.5. U^{VI} passed through the column, In^{III} was eluted with 0.01M HNO₃, Ce^{IV} with 1M HNO₃ and Zr^{IV} with 4M HNO₃. A mixture of In^{III}, Co^{II}, Cr^{III} and Tl^{III} was passed through the column at pH 4.5. Co^{II} passed through the column, In^{III} was eluted with 0.01 M HNO₃, Cr^{III} with 1 M

Fig. 1. Separation of In^{III} from multicomponent mixture.

H₂SO₄ and Tl^{III} with 2 M NaCl. A mixture of In^{III}, Cd^{II}, Cr^{III} and Zr^{IV} in acetate buffer at pH 4.5 was passed through the column when all the elements were extracted excepting Cd. In^{III} was eluted with 0.01 M HNO₃, Cr^{III} with 1 M H₂SO₄ and Zr^{IV} with 4 M HNO₃.

Elution behaviour of indium in multicomponent mixtures is given in Fig. 1.

References

1. F. W. E. STRELOW and A. H. VICTOR, *Talanta*, 1972, **19**, 1019.
2. R. B. HEDDUR and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 881.
3. B. K. PREOBRAZHENSKI and G. S. KARTYKHIN, *Radiokhimiya*, 1962, **4**, 536.
4. U. S. RAY and S. C. MODOK, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 933.
5. A. K. DE and U. S. RAY, *Sep. Sci.*, 1971, **6**, 67.
6. R. PRIBIL, "Chelometry, Basic Determination", Chemapol, Praha, 1961.
7. R. B. HEDDUR and S. M. KHOPKAR, *J. Liquid Chromatogr.*, 1983, **8**, 95.